

Genomics of *Brevibacterium* strains reveal adaptations necessary to acclimatize in different marine environments

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ABSTRACT

Microbes are ubiquitous throughout the seawater and underlying sediment, which covers the vast region of the earth surface. Strains of different genera under the phylum *Actinobacteria* are ubiquitous all-over different environments of the earth surfaces. A well-studied aerobic genus, *Brevibacterium*, under the phylum also found to be omnipresent in both marine and terrestrial environments, ranging from coastal to open ocean. Which raise question, whether marine strains are phylogenetically distinct from others or not, and what are the special genomic adaptation marine strains acquire. To examine these, core and pan genome was studied for all the pure culture-based genomes of different strains under *Brevibacterium* genus. Both, 325 core genes-based as well as gene presence-absence matrix-based i.e. the contribution pattern of each genome to form the pan genome) phylogenetic analysis reveals that marine strains are distributed in polyphyletic clade but share adjacent position in phylograms, suggesting that special marine adaptation affects the genome evolution for isolates living in marine habitat. Starting from considering all the available genomes, different geographical province-specific (Atlantic Ocean, Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean) genomic datasets were created, following core and pan genome analysis was performed for all the dataset. Which reveals that for marine adaptation 1638 number of core genes are essential, as these genes incorporated in all the genomes of marine strains under the genus *Brevibacterium*. Core genome expansion for genomes of Indian Ocean isolates and Arabian Sea oxygen minimum zone (OMZ) sediment's isolates were further studied in details, which depicts gene-encoding proteins involved in cell size adjustment, DNA repair machinery, heavy metal resistance, ions transport and other functions, becomes integrated into core genome and found to be pivotal genetic features for living nearby oceanic territory of OMZ. This marine province-specific core genome expansion study shows that strains despite belonging to different species level taxonomic group, possess ecologically significant core genes. A possible relation found to be existed in between seabed expansion, which creates new marine provinces in million years of time scale, and geographical province-specific microbial core genome evolution.

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INTRODUCTION

Strains of the phylum *Actinobacteria* are ubiquitous in most of the natural environments, regardless of the environmental harshness, their habitat ranges from fresh to saline waterbodies and sediment systems of the both, hot springs, and soil of arid deserts (Ward and Bora 2006; Valverde et al. 2012; Mohammadipanah and Wink
40 2016; Neuenschwander et al. 2018; Deng et al. 2020). The genus *Brevibacterium*, can be regarded as typical under the phylum, as strains under it follows the similar habitability range (Chen et al. 2016; Jung et al. 2018; Belov et al. 2019; Pei et al. 2020; Zhao et al. 2023). Strains under the genus are generally obligately aerobic, gram positive, non-spore former (Collins 2006).

Global ocean and its sediment system is the largest interconnected microbial habitat (Hoshino et al. 2020). The
45 vast oceanic territory is generally divided into four major provinces, Pacific Ocean, Atlantic Ocean, Indian Ocean and Antarctic/Southern Ocean. Different physical and geochemical, characteristics of an environment are the driving force for the selection of only microorganisms possessing adaptive physiological traits necessary to sustain *in situ* (Dmitrijeva et al. 2024). In a particular environmental niche, ecological selection pressures affect the genome evolution through different mechanisms of genome alteration, such as spontaneous mutation and
50 gain/loss of gene's functions; among these mechanisms horizontal transfer of genes encoding key survival features, between taxonomically diverse individuals is a highly effective way of genomic adaptation (Arnold et al. 2022). Strains of the *Brevibacterium*, are ubiquitous in the different geographic regions of the global marine territory. They are reported to be isolated from water/sediment sample of different regions of Pacific Ocean (Lee 2008, Pei et al. 2021), Atlantic Ocean (Pei et al. 2021), Indian Ocean (Bhadra et al. 2008; Chen et al. 2016).

55 The aim of the current study is to examine how marine habitat-specific genome evolution takes place for strains of the *Brevibacterium* genus, which is distributed in both coastal to open ocean environment. Core and pan genome-based phylogenetic analysis were performed for all the pure culture strains under the genus to examine mono- or poly-phyletic origin of marine strains and relatedness between them. Core and pan genome functional analysis were done for all the pure culture isolate's genome, available under the genus *Brevibacterium* to reveal
60 the actual size of the core and pan genome. How core genome expansion occurs for adaptation in marine habitat was examined (genes those added in the core genome only when genomes of marine strains considered). Further, core and pan genome analysis was done for different subsets of genomes obtained from isolates living in different marine provinces, which would reveal how core genome structure changes in accordance with the changes in marine provinces. Genomic adaptation to Indian ocean province was focused in detail along with special genomic
65 features necessary to live in Arabian Sea OMZ sediment. Result of marine province specific genomic group/subset analysis was used to evaluate how distinct geographical territories shape core genome structure and functions of different strains of *Brevibacterium*. Furthermore, genomic plasticity of the marine isolates was analyzed by recently incorporated genes through horizontal gene transfer, in each of the marine isolate's genome. The study will add new understandings on how genome divergence is shaped by niche differentiation which is resulted from
70 different geophysical conditions of earth.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Genome of pure culture isolates available on GenBank

138 number of genome assemblies is available in GenBank database of National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), under the genus *Brevibacterium* (as on March 2024). These only include all the genome assemblies under the genus which, derived from pure culture isolates, having proper annotation as well as proper taxonomic status (followed categorization of NCBI) and retrieved on March, 2024. The 138 genome assemblies include 25 complete genomes and 33 genomes from 'type material' (under the genus 37 species have validly published). It was found that these strains were isolated from diverse habitats ranging from milk products, human infections, soil, freshwater or marine sediment systems. Genomes (represented by single complete circular chromosome) of *Brevibacterium* sp. BDFS002 and *Brevibacterium* sp. JSBI002 strains, isolated from Arabian Sea OMZ sediment system (Sarkar et al. 2024) were also included within 138 genome assemblies. TYGS (type strain genome server, DSMZ) was used to determine genome based taxonomic position whenever needed for the strains those have not species level taxonomic status (Meier-Kolthoff JP and Göker 2019).

Grouping of *Brevibacterium* strains on the basis of marine provinces

Six hierarchical genome groups were formed concerning the niches from which pure culture of different *Brevibacterium* strains reported to be isolated i.e. on the basis of the characteristics/geographical region of the habitat from which 138 strains were isolated. All_Genomes dataset include all the 138 genomes of respective strains, found to be isolated from diverse environmental habitats (Supplementary Table S1). Marine_Genomes dataset include all the genome of strains those were isolated from seawater or marine sediment (genomes those were found to be obtained from strains present in seafood, not included, as geographic location of the seafood from which strain was isolated may not the actual geographic location of the habitat where strain naturally occurs). Atlantic_Ocean_Genomes dataset was created which includes three genomes of respective strains, isolated from water or sediment system of Atlantic Ocean. Pacific_Ocean_Genomes dataset was created including the four genomes those were isolated from water or sediment sample of Pacific Ocean territories. Indian_Ocean_Genomes dataset was created including all the six genomes isolated from strains living in geographic territories of Indian Ocean. Whereas, Arabian_Sea_Genomes dataset include genomes obtained from two pure culture strains isolated from OMZ sediment of Arabian Sea.

Core and pan genome analysis and phylogeny

Bacterial pan genome analysis pipeline (BPGA, version 1.3; Chaudhari et al. 2016) was used to determine pan and core genome of six hierarchical habitat-based group of strains distributed under the genus *Brevibacterium*. For orthologous clustering of genes, USEARCH algorithm (Edgar 2010) was used and 50% identity value was used as cutoff for clustering all the genes present in all the genomes of a given dataset. Six groups of genome assemblies were separately used to determine pan and core genome of respective group of strains. Pan genome

describes distribution of all genes of a given dataset, in different orthologous gene families; pan genome includes core genes (genes present in each genome of a dataset), accessory genes (genes present in two or more genomes of a dataset) and unique genes (genes present in specific genome but not in others). Non-redundant reference sequences (RefSeq) of core, accessory and unique genes of any of the genomic dataset was extracted through BPGA script. After orthologous clustering of the all genes found in all genomes of a dataset, pan and core genome curve was plotted. Pan genome curve depict number of new gene families added after addition of each genome. Core genome curve illustrates how addition of genomes reduces the number of different gene families present throughout the genomes of each dataset. Using BPGA scripts 20 number of random permutations were carried out for addition of each genome and considering median values of number of all distinct gene families and number of commonly shared gene families of a given dataset to determine pan and core genome of that dataset to removing any biases. Power regression model was used for pan genome data and exponential model was used for core genome data for plotting pan and core genome curve and to determine whether pan genome is closed or open (Chaudhari et al. 2016). All the genes of a genome, those contain atypical G+C content (if G+C contents of a gene deviate from the average G+C content of the genome by more than two times of the standard deviation) was determined by atypical GC content analysis script of BPGA (Chaudhari et al. 2016). This atypical GC content of a gene indicate possible inclusion within the respective genome through horizontal gene transfer.

Phylogenetic analysis was performed by considering both core genome and pan genome of all the 138 strains. For core genome based phylogenetic analysis, core genes were used for multiple sequences alignments by MUSCLE software (Edgar 2004). For pan genome based phylogenetic analysis, gene presence and absence based binary pan-matrix was considered for all the 138 genomes. Similarity and dissimilarity in contribution of genes to pan genome (orthologous gene clusters) was used to calculate gene matrix. Phylogenetic tree by neighbor-joining approach was created for both core genome and pan genome and Bio-Phylo-v2.0.1 was used for drawing phylogenetic tree (Vos et al. 2011).

Annotation of core, accessory and unique genes

Web-based utilities of eggNOG-mapper was used to functional identification of core, accessory and unique genes of a genomic dataset when required (Cantalapiedra et al. 2021). For this eggNOG 5 database was searched for a given query using search filters Minimum hit e-value = 0.001, Minimum hit bit-score = 60, Percentage identity = 40, Minimum % of query coverage = 20 and Minimum % of subject coverage = 20.

RESULTS

Range of habitability and genomic characteristics of pure cultured strains

Genome assembly data was retrieved from the GenBank database for all pure-culture strains under *Brevibacterium* genus (138 strains), reported to be isolated from diverse environmental habitat such as, human infection, dairy product, soil, freshwater and marine sediment (Table 1; Supplementary Table S1). Among these 138 genome assemblies, 13 were found to be isolated from strains lining in marine environment and having proper geographical area from which sample of the inoculum obtained. These 13 marine strains were spread over three marine provinces; three were isolated from Atlantic Ocean, six were isolated from Indian Ocean (two from Arabian Sea OMZ sediment) and four were isolated from Pacific Ocean (Figure 1). Among these 13 strains 9 strains were taxonomically classified up to species level taxon; genome of remaining four were analyzed by TYGS. All the four were found to belong new species as none of these show > 70% dDDH value with genomes of any type strain of *Brevibacterium* (Table 1).

Genome assembly size of all 138 genomes of All_Genomes dataset, ranges from 2.3 Mb to 4.7 Mb having CheckM determined completeness 75.5% to 98.7%; whereas, G+C percentage ranging from 58% to 73%. Genome assembly size for 13 genomes of Marine_Genomes dataset ranges from 3.7 Mb to 4.5 Mb; for these genomes' completeness ranges from 88.3% to 97.7% and G+C percentage ranges from 63% to 66% (Figure 2; Table 1; Supplementary Table S1).

Overall core and pan genome structure and phylogeny

Orthologous clustering of total gene repertoire of 138 genomes, obtained from all pure culture strains under the genus *Brevibacterium*, resulted in 325 number of non-redundant RefSeq genes shared by all the strains and regarded as core genome (Supplementary Table S2). Along with, 27914 number of non-redundant RefSeq genes can be obtained, within which all the genomic repertoire of 138 genomes were distributed, constituting the pan genome. To determine whether pan genome is open or closed, pan genome data was fitted on power regression model [on the equation $f(x) = a \cdot x^b$ where the value of a, x and b found to be as follows: $a = 3674.6$, $x = 138$ and $b = 0.4$] it was revealed that the pan genome is still open (as the value of $b \leq 1$) i.e. gene from new orthologous families is still being added in the gene pool of *Brevibacterium* strains (Figure 3).

Phylogenetic tree derived by multiple sequence alignment of the 325 core genes, resulted in a phylogram (Figure 4) where different species level clusters existed on different node. 12 out of the 13 marine strains situated adjacent position on the phylogenetic tree. While only *Brevibacterium* sp. BDJS002 positioned distantly (Figure 4). Pan genome-based phylogeny was analyzed, considering each genome's contribution in the pangenome structure, through gene presence-absence data matrix (Figure 5). Here also similar distribution of marine strains observed. Pan genome constitute the non-redundant gene set of core, accessory (genes available in two or more genome) and unique genes (genes only available in a particular genome under consideration) determined through orthologous clustering. Highest percentage of (16.9%) non-redundant core genes were distributed in the J

(Translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis) COG category. Most percentage of non-redundant accessory genes were distributed in K (Transcription) COG category. Highest number of non-redundant unique genes for all the 138 genomes were found to be distributed in also the K (Transcription) COG category. For both accessory and unique genes distribution 2nd highest distribution was found to be in E (Amino acid transport and metabolism) COG category (R COG category was not taking under consideration for this ranking as this category includes only genes those are predicted to be involved in general function). Along with this, core genes were found to be distributed with values more than 5% in M (Cell wall/membrane/envelope biogenesis), O (Post-translational modification, protein turnover, and chaperones), L (Replication, recombination and repair), C (Energy production and conversion), E (Amino acid transport and metabolism), H (Coenzyme transport and metabolism) and I (Lipid transport and metabolism) COG categories. Whereas, more than 5% accessory genes found to distributed in L (Replication, recombination and repair), G (Carbohydrate transport and metabolism), and P (Inorganic ion transport and metabolism) COG categories. More than 5% unique genes were distributed in G (Carbohydrate transport and metabolism), I (Lipid transport and metabolism), Q (Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport, and catabolism) and P (Inorganic ion transport and metabolism) COG categories individually (Figure 6A; Supplementary Table S3).

Core genome expansion for marine habitat adaptation

After orthologous clustering of total gene repertoire of 13 marine strains of *Brevibacterium*, 1963 non-redundant genes were found to be shared by all genomes i.e. representing the core genome size for the marine strains (Supplementary Table S4). The overall pan genome for these marine strains represented by 7788 number of non-redundant genes. After fitting pan genome data on power regression model [$f(x) = a \cdot x^b$ where the value of a, x and b found to be as follows: $a = 3456.8$, $x = 13$ and $b = 0.3$], it was found that it is still open in nature.

Different COG categories found to be enriched in core, accessory and unique gene sets of the pan genome. Highest percentage (13.5%) of core genes were distributed in E (Amino acid transport and metabolism) COG category. Most percentages of accessory genes (13.8% and 13.1%) were found to be distributed in K (Transcription) and E COG categories respectively. For unique genes distribution in COG categories, the K (Transcription) category was found to be the highest. More than 5% core, accessory and unique genes were distributed in K (Transcription), C (Energy production and conversion), G (Carbohydrate transport and metabolism), E (Amino acid transport and metabolism) and P (Inorganic ion transport and metabolism) COG categories individually (Figure 6B; Supplementary Table S3). After annotating these all 1963 number of core genes against KEGG database it was found that Membrane transport, Signal transduction (under major KEGG category - Environmental Information Processing), Folding, sorting and degradation, Replication and repair, Translation (under major KEGG category - Genetic Information Processing), Amino acid metabolism, Carbohydrate metabolism, Energy metabolism, Nucleotide metabolism (under major KEGG category - Metabolisms) KEGG sub-category become enriched in core genome of marine strains (Supplementary Table S5).

Core genome that enriches for marine adaptation must be the results of subtraction of 325 non-redundant core genes of all the strains, from non-redundant core genes of marine strains. Thus $(1963-325) = 1638$ number of core genes might be essential for marine adaptation. When annotated on KEGG database, the 1638 number of core genes found to be distributed in all the COG categories (Supplementary Table S6). COG category-wise important genes and functional description of their encoded proteins include,

- Under COG category D (cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning), genes (*ftsK*, *ftsX*, *ftsW*, *parA*, *scpB*, *sepF* and *smc*) encoding proteins involved in cell division and chromosome segregation
- Under COG category M (cell wall/membrane/envelope biogenesis), genes encoding proteins involved in, first step of hexosamine metabolism (*glmS*), cell wall formation (*mraY*, *murB*, *murD*, *murG*, *murI*), catalyzes the interconversion of L-alanine and D- alanine (*alr*), mechanosensitive ion channel (*mscS*), regulation of osmotic pressure changes within the cell (*mscL*)
- Under COG category O (post-translational modification, protein turnover, and chaperones), genes encoding proteins involved in quality control of integral membrane protein (*ftsH*), proper folding of polypeptides in stressed condition (*groL*), different chaperones (*clpP*, *clpX*), response to hyperosmotic and heat shock by preventing the aggregation of stress-denatured proteins (*grpE*), redoxin (*resA*), thioredoxin (*trxA*), glutaredoxin (*nrdH*), heat shock protein (*hsp18*), degradation of misfolded proteins (*clpP*), glycoprotease (*yeaZ*), cytochrome oxidase assembly (*ctaA*, *ctaB*)
- Under COG category T (signal transduction mechanisms), genes encoding proteins involved in, ammonia assimilation (*glnE*), mediator of the stringent response that coordinates a variety of cellular activities in response to changes in nutritional abundance (*relA*), sensor kinase (*citA*), tyrosine kinase (*pknA*), transcriptional regulatory protein (*cseB*)
- Under COG category U (intracellular trafficking, secretion, and vesicular transport), genes encoding, part of the Sec protein translocase complex (*secA*, *secD*, *secE*), type II/IV secretion system protein (*cpaF*), proteins involved in targeting and insertion of nascent membrane proteins into the cytoplasmic membrane (*ffh*)
- Under COG category V (defense mechanisms) genes encoding, uncharacterized beta-lactamase and proteins from AcrB/AcrD/AcrF family
- Under COG category J (translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis), gene encoding ribosomal proteins (*rpsA* to *rpsD*, *rpsF* to *rpsH*, *rpsJ*, *rpsK*, *rpsM* to *rpsT*, *rplA*, *rplC*, *rplD*, *rplF*, *rplI* to *rplQ*, *rplS*, *rplU* to *rplX*) and translational termination proteins (*prfA* to *prfC*)
- Under COG category K (transcription), genes coding, primary sigma factor responsible for sigmoidal growth (*sigA*), uncharacterized bacterial transcriptional regulators, regulators of arginine biosynthesis genes (*argR*), regulatory protein (*hspR*), cold shock protein (*scoF4*), proteins needed for assembly of RNA polymerase (*rpoZ*)

- 245 - Under COG category L (replication, recombination and repair), gene encoding, DNA alkylation repair enzyme (*alkB*, *alkD*), DNA polymerase and associated proteins (*dnaA*, *dnaB*, *dnaE2*, *dnaG*, *dnaN*, *dnaQ*, *dnaX*, *polA*), recombination related proteins (*recB*, *recF*, *recG*, *recN*, *recQ*, *recQ*, *recR*), DNA damage recognition and processing protein machinery (*uvrA*, *uvrD2*, *uvrC*)
- Under COG category C (energy production and conversion), genes encoding, component of the pyruvate dehydrogenase (*aceA*, *aceE*), regulators of arginine biosynthesis genes (*argR*), different subunit of ATP synthase (*atpA*, *atpB*, *atpC*, *atpE*, *atpF*, *atpG*), Sodium: dicarboxylate symporter (*gltT*)
- 250 - Under COG category G (carbohydrate transport and metabolism), genes encoding, phosphoglucomutase/phosphomannomutase (*manB*), phosphomannose isomerase type I (*manA*), glycosyl hydrolases (*otsB*), glycosyltransferase (*otsA*), phosphofructokinase (*pfkA*), bacterial extracellular solute-binding protein (*smoE*)
- 255 - Under COG category E (carbohydrate transport and metabolism), gene encoding, arginine synthase and lyase family proteins (*argB*, *argC*, *argE*, *argF*, *argG*, *argH*, *argJ*), proteins involved in shikimate compound related metabolism (*aroA*, *aroB*, *aroE*, *aroK*, *aroQ*), proteins responsible for the synthesis of L- tryptophan (*trpA*, *trpB*, *trpC*)
- 260 - Under COG category F (nucleotide transport and metabolism), genes encoding, adenosine/AMP deaminase (*add*), carbamoyl-phosphate synthase (*carA*, *carB*), orotidine 5'-phosphate decarboxylase/HUMPS family (*pyrF*), enzyme that catalyzes the reversible phosphorylation of UMP to UDP (*pyrH*), CO dehydrogenase (*xdhA*), aldehyde oxidase and xanthine dehydrogenase (*xdhB*), enzyme that catalyzes the synthesis of GMP from XMP (*guaA*)
- 265 - Under COG category H (coenzyme transport and metabolism), gene encoding proteins that, catalyzes the phosphorylation of the 3'-hydroxyl group of dephosphocoenzyme A to form coenzyme A (*coaE*), reversibly transfers an adenylyl group from ATP to 4'- phosphopantetheine (*coaD*), catalyzes the NADPH-dependent reduction of glutamyl- tRNA (Glu) to glutamate 1-semialdehyde (*hemA*), have different enzymatic function (*nadA* to *nadE*, *thiD* to *thiG*, *thiL*, *thiM*)
- 270 - Under COG category I (lipid transport and metabolism), gene encoding different transferases (*accD1*, *acpS*, *acpP*), AMP-binding enzyme (*fadD*), thiolase (*fadI*), acyl transferase (*fabD*)
- Under COG category P (inorganic ion transport and metabolism), gene encoding, catalase (*kataA*), bifunctional enzyme with both catalase and broad- spectrum peroxidase activity (*katG*), sodium/hydrogen exchanger family protein (*kefB*), NADH-Ubiquinone oxidoreductase complex I (*mrpA/mrpB*), NADH-ubiquinone/plastoquinone oxidoreductase (*mrpC*), Proton-conducting membrane transporter (*mrpD*), Na⁺/H⁺ ion antiporter subunit (*mrpE*, *mrpG*), binding-protein-dependent transport system inner membrane component (*oppB*), N-terminal TM domain of oligopeptide transport permease C (*oppC*), ABC transporter permease (*oppC4*), proteins that destroys radicals which are normally produced within the cells and which are toxic to biological systems (*sodA*)
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280 Marine province-specific core genome expansion

Core and pan genome analysis for each of the three marine province-specific genomic dataset reveals that, core genome was represented by 2572, 2376 and 2243 number of non-redundant core genes for Atlantic_Ocean_Genomes, Pacific_Ocean_Genomes and Indian_Ocean_Genomes (Supplementary Tables S7, S8 and S9). Pan genome was represented by 4711, 5780 and 5462 number of non-redundant genes. Each of the pan genome was found open when pan genome data was fitted on above mentioned power regression model.

From the above result, it was revealed that core genome of strains isolated from Atlantic Ocean, Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean get expanded by 609, 413 and 280 number of core genes (Figure 7A). Annotation of these genes with eggNOG 5 database revealed that these core genes distributed over most of the COG categories (Figure 7B; Supplementary Table S10). COG category-wise important genes and functional description, which were added in the core genome of *Brevibacterium* strains living in Indian Ocean province, and their encoded proteins include,

- Under COG category M, gene encoding proteins involved in, cell wall formation, catalyzes the final step in the synthesis of UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-pentapeptide (*murF*), catalyzes the conversion of 1-hydroxy-2-methyl-2-(E)-butenyl 4-diphosphate (HMBPP) into a mixture of isopentenyl diphosphate (IPP) and dimethylallyl diphosphate (*ispH*), UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 2-epimerase (*wecB*), CoA-binding domain (*capD*), belongs to the DapA family (*dapA_1*)
- Under COG category T, gene encoding proteins involved in, response regulator which acts during transcriptional antitermination (*pdtar*), forkhead associated domain
- Under COG category U, gene encoding proteins involved in membrane protein translocation (*secF*, *secG*), Tfp pilus assembly protein FimV, preprotein translocase, involved in the tonB-independent uptake of proteins
- Under COG category J, gene encoding proteins involved in mRNA degradation which catalyzes the phosphorolysis of single-stranded polyribonucleotides processively in the 3'- to 5'-direction (*pnp*), one of the primary rRNA binding proteins required for association of the 30S and 50S subunits to form the 70S ribosome (*rplB*), binds directly to 23S rRNA and is necessary for the in vitro assembly process of the 50S ribosomal subunit (*rplT*), Interacts with and stabilizes bases of the 16S rRNA that are involved in tRNA selection (*rpsL*), ribosomal protein S9/S16 (*rpsI*).
- Under COG category K, gene encoding proteins, putative response regulator, deoxyribose operon repressor, proteins that participates in transcription elongation, termination and antitermination (*nusG*), protein involved in negative regulation of DNA-templated transcription initiation, proteins involved in transcription antitermination (*nusB*), addiction module antidote protein (*higA*)
- Under COG category L, gene encoding proteins, that releases the supercoiling and torsional tension of DNA (*topA*), topoisomerase II (*gyrB2*), type III restriction enzyme, res subunit (*sdrA*), DNA polymerase III delta subunit (*holB*), with LigD forms a non-homologous end joining DNA repair enzyme, which

- 315 repairs dsDNA breaks with reduced fidelity (*ku*), involved in DNA repair and RecF pathway recombination (*recO*), 3'-to-5' exonuclease (*orn*), the RuvA-RuvB complex in the presence of ATP renatures cruciform structure in supercoiled DNA with palindromic sequence (*ruvA*)
- Under COG category C, gene encoding proteins, 2-oxoglutarate dehydrogenase, prokaryotic cytochrome b561, acetyl-CoA hydrolase/transferase C-terminal domain (*catI*), produces ATP from ADP in the presence of a proton gradient across the membrane (*atpD*), succinyl-CoA synthetase functions in the citric acid cycle (*sucC*), belongs to the cytochrome c oxidase bacterial subunit CtaF family (*ctaF*)
 - 320 - Under COG category G, gene encoding proteins, alpha-L-arabinofuranosidase, GntP family permease (*gntT*), glycoside hydrolases, catalyzes the reversible conversion of 2-phosphoglycerate into phosphoenolpyruvate (*eno*), glucosamine-6-phosphate isomerases/6-phosphogluconolactonase (*nagB*)
 - 325 - Under COG category E, gene encoding proteins involved in, class-II DAHP synthetase family (*aroG*), type I 3-dehydroquinase (*aroD*), rifampin ADP-ribosyl transferase (*arr*), phosphoribosyl-ATP pyrophosphohydrolase (*hisE*), IGPS catalyzes the conversion of PRFAR and glutamine to IGP, AICAR and glutamate (*hisH*)
 - Under COG category F, gene encoding proteins that catalyzes the ATP-dependent amination of UTP to CTP with either L-glutamine or ammonia as the source of nitrogen (*pyrG*), catalyzes the conversion of dihydroorotate to orotate with quinone as electron acceptor (*pyrD*), plays an important role in the de novo pathway of purine nucleotide biosynthesis (*purA*), catalyzes a salvage reaction resulting in the formation of AMP (*apt*)
 - 330 - Under COG category H, gene encoding protein that catalyzes two steps in the biosynthesis of coenzyme A (*coaBC*), catalyzes the conversion of dethiobiotin to biotin (*bioB*), catalyzes the NADPH-dependent reduction of ketopantoate into pantoic acid (*apbA*), catalyzes the ferrous insertion into protoporphyrin IX (*hemH*), catalyzes the synthesis of beta-nicotinate D- ribonucleotide from nicotinate and 5-phospho-D-ribose 1-phosphate at the expense of ATP (*pncB*)
 - 335 - Under COG category I, gene encoding, acyltransferase, short chain fatty acid transporter (*atoE*), synthesis of isoprenoid compounds (*ispF* to *ispH*), squalene/phytoene synthase (*crtB*)
 - 340 - Under COG category P, gene encoding putative citrate transporter, ammonium transporter (*amt*), formate/nitrite transporter (*focA*), CorA-like Mg²⁺ transporter protein (*corA*), heme oxygenase (*hmuO*)

The two *Brevibacterium* strains of Arabian Sea OMZ isolates share additional 208 number of core genes in addition to the shared core genome of six isolates from Indian Ocean region. The 208 genes are distributed in most of the COG categories (Supplementary Tables S11 and S12). COG category-wise important genes and functional description of their encoded proteins include,

- Under COG category M, gene encoding proteins for, bacterial sugar transferase (*epsL*), DegT/DnrJ/EryC1/StrS aminotransferase (*epsN*), putative lysyltransferase, putative epimerase

- 350 - Under COG category O, gene encoding proteins for, C-terminal four TMM region of protein-O-mannosyltransferase (*pmt*), putative ADP-ribosylglycohydrolase, putative XdhC Rossmann domain
- Under COG category T, gene encoding proteins for, 5TM C-terminal transporter carbon starvation CstA (*cstA*), forkhead associated domain (*garA*), low molecular weight phosphotyrosine protein phosphatase, low molecular weight phosphatase family (*arsC*)
- Under COG category U, gene encoding, putative signal peptidase, putative oxidoreductase
- 355 - Under COG category J, gene encoding amidase (*amiD*), putative acetyltransferases, putative N-acetylases of ribosomal proteins, proteins polyketide cyclase
- Under COG category K, gene encoding proteins involved in, trisaccharide binding, ParB-like nuclease domain (*parB*), putative GCN5-related N-acetyltransferase, iron dependent repressor, arsenical resistance operon repressor (*cmtR*), cold shock protein domain (*scoF4*)
- 360 - Under COG category L, gene encoding, DNA polymerase involved in damage-induced mutagenesis and translesion synthesis (*dnaE2*), sigma-70 factor, transposase, integrase core domain, helix-turn-helix domain of resolvase, excinuclease ABC activity
- Under COG category L, gene encoding, xanthine dehydrogenase, Na⁺/H⁺ antiporter (*nhaC*), Belongs to the class-I pyridine nucleotide-disulfide oxidoreductase family (*merA*), malate/L-lactate dehydrogenase
- 365 - Under COG category G, gene encoding phosphodiester glycosidase, glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase, trehalose-phosphatase, NmrA family protein
- Under COG category E, gene encoding proteins involved in thiamine pyrophosphate, central domain (*mdlC*), pyridoxal-dependent decarboxylase, catalyzes the transfer of a methyl group from 5-methyltetrahydrofolate to homocysteine resulting in methionine formation (*metE*), belongs to the carbamate kinase family (*arcC*), hydroxymethylglutaryl-CoA lyase (*hmgL*), ATPases associated with a variety of cellular activities (*gluA*)
- 370 - Under COG category H, gene encoding 6-pyruvoyl tetrahydropterin synthase (*ptpS*)
- Under COG category I, gene encoding proteins belongs to the HMG-CoA reductase family, acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, C-terminal domain (*gcdH*), putative oxidoreductase
- 375 - Under COG category P, gene encoding, anion-transporting ATPase (*arsA*), sodium bile acid symporter family (*arsB*), flavin-binding monooxygenase-like (*arsO*), ATPases associated with a variety of cellular activities (*feuA*), FecCD transport family (*feuC*), periplasmic binding protein (*feuS*), chromate transporter (*chrA*), Na⁺/H⁺ antiporter that extrudes sodium in exchange for external protons (*nhaA*)

380 **Actively evolving genome of marine isolates**

Genes for which G+C content deviate from the average G+C content of respected genome by more than two times of the standard deviation, was identified by BPGA scripts (Chaudhari et al. 2016). These are the genes which may

be integrated in the respective genome through different horizontal gene transfer mechanism. When 13 genomes of marine strains of *Brevibacterium* was analyzed for genes having atypical G+C content it was found that all the 13 genomes contain unique genes with atypical G+C content. When these atypical G+C content bearing genes for all the 13 marine isolates, were annotated against KEGG database by eggNOG mapper it was found that they fall under different orthologous groups (eggNOG_OGs; Supplementary Table S13).

- In the genome of *Brevibacterium atlanticum* WO024, out of 33 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 4 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 24 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 1 from family Brevibacteriaceae), 3 genes were annotated in orthologous group pf Proteobacteria, 2 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Firmicutes. The function of these genes includes transcription regulation (*carD*, *ybcM*), putative sugar transporter, proteins involved in mercury resistance, type I restriction modification DNA specificity domain (*hsdM*).
- In the genome of *Brevibacterium pigmentatum* YB235, out of 14 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 1 gene was annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 11 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 1 from family Brevibacteriaceae), 3 genes were annotated in orthologous group pf Proteobacteria, 1 gene were annotated in orthologous group of Cyanobacteria. The function of these genes includes response regulator, adenine specific DNA methylase, type III restriction enzyme, res subunit, ATPase, P-type transporting (*cybH*).
- In the genome of *Brevibacterium oceani* WW007, out of 39 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 4 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 32 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 1 from family Brevibacteriaceae), 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group pf Proteobacteria, 2 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Firmicutes. The function of these genes includes transcriptional regulator, ABC transporter, bacterial extracellular solute-binding protein, sugar transporter, ABC-type nitrate sulfonate bicarbonate transport systems periplasmic components.
- In the genome of *Brevibacterium* sp. BDJS002, out of 29 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 4 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 24 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 9 genes from family Brevibacteriaceae), 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group of Bacteroidetes. The function of these genes includes restriction endonuclease, death-on-curing family protein, resolvase, cytochrome c biogenesis protein transmembrane region, region found in RelA/SpoT proteins (*ywaC*).
- In the genome of *Brevibacterium* sp. JSBI002, out of 21 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 19 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while no genes from family Brevibacteriaceae), 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group pf Proteobacteria, 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group of Firmicutes. The function of these genes includes glycosyltransferase, endonuclease, transposase, putative ATP-dependent Lon protease, belongs to the peptidase S8, bacterial toxin 35.

- 420 - In the genome of *Brevibacterium oceani* BBH7, out of 23 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 4 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Viruses, 2 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 15 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while no genes from family Brevibacteriaceae), 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group of Firmicutes, 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group of Bacteroidetes. The function of these genes includes transcriptional regulator, DNA alkylation repair, endonuclease, viral recombinase domain.
- 425 - In the genome of *Brevibacterium sediminis* COD27, out of 31 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 2 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 22 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 6 from family Brevibacteriaceae), 4 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Proteobacteria, 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group of Bacteroidetes, 2 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Firmicutes. The function of these genes includes, amidinotransferase, transposase, nucleotidyl transferase, AbiEii toxin, arsenite transmembrane transporter, Na⁺/H⁺ antiporter.
- 430 - In the genome of *Brevibacterium limosum* o2, out of 34 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 4 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 30 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 3 from family Brevibacteriaceae). The function of these genes includes different glycosyl transferases (family 1, 2, 4), sigma-70 region 2, sugar transporter.
- 435 - In the genome of *Brevibacterium marinum* DSM 18964, out of 30 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 6 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 23 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 1 from family Brevibacteriaceae), 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group of Firmicutes. The function of these genes includes transposases, protein possibly involved in utilization of glycolate and propanediol, different hydrolases activity.
- 440 - In the genome of *Brevibacterium* sp. CCUG 69071, out of 30 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 1 gene was annotated in the orthologous group of Viruses, 28 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 1 from family Brevibacteriaceae), 1 gene was annotated in orthologous group of Firmicutes. The function of these genes includes glycosyltransferase, transcriptional regulator, endonucleases, recombinase.
- 445 - In the genome of *Brevibacterium* sp. Marine, out of 37 unique genes having atypical G+C content, 3 genes were annotated up to orthologous group of Bacteria, 1 gene was annotated up to orthologous group of Archaea, 26 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Actinobacteria (while 5 from family Brevibacteriaceae), 4 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Proteobacteria, 3 genes were annotated in orthologous group of Firmicutes. The function of these genes includes glycosyl transferases, aromatic amino acid lyase, reverse transcriptase, sodium solute symporter, DNA mismatch endonuclease (vsr).
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In the genome of *Brevibacterium sediminis* FXJ8.269 and *Brevibacterium sediminis* CGMCC 1.15472 have no unique genes.

DISCUSSIONS

Microbial metabolism in marine gets influenced by *in situ* physico-chemical features of the habitat, diversity of metabolisms differs in coastal seawater-sediment system from open ocean site's seawater-sediment system (D'Hondt et al. 2009; D'Hondt et al. 2015; Sarkar et al. 2022). Seawater and underlying sediment of a particular marine environment functions as environmental continuum, microbial metabolism taking place within a sediment system get influenced by its overlying seawater, which is the only way for nutrient supply (Marcus and Boero, 1998). Depending on the physico-chemical features such as sedimentation rate, bottom water oxygen availability, abundance of oxidized/reduced metallic ions different metabolic stratum existed in the marine sedimentary environment (Kallmeyer et al. 2012; D'Hondt et al. 2015; Torres-Beltrán et al. 2021). Though microbial community changes from coastal region to open ocean sites, aerobic strains of proteobacteria and actinobacteria found to be ubiquitous in distribution (Batzke et al. 2007; Bhattacharya et al. 2020, Sarkar et al. 2024) throughout the global marine habitat. Despite the extreme environmental condition in different marine provinces, wide distribution of aerobic bacteria throughout the marine system raises question about their adaptation. Genomic adaptation regarding microbial life in marine habitat was studied for the strains of an aerobic genus, *Brevibacterium*, revealing its marine origin and expanded core genome structure for adapting different marine provinces.

Polyphyletic genome evolution for marine strains

G+C content percentages and genomic sizes are distributed in narrow range when only marine strains were taken under consideration (Figures 2A and 2B; Supplementary Table S1) in comparison to all the 138 strains. This indicates, structurally genomes of the marine strains not fall apart. After orthologous clustering of all the genes of 138 genomes, 325 non-redundant genes were identified representing core genome. Major percentages of 325 non-redundant core genes were assigned to the translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis metabolism indicating their important and central role in surviving/growing microbial life. But as all the strains under the genus is Gram-positive and have capabilities to adapt in diverse environmental habitat significant number of genes concerning cell wall formation, replication, energy production and conversion, amino acid transport and metabolism becomes conserved (Supplementary Table S2). The pangenome is still open indicating the adaptive possibilities of strains in adverse environmental condition.

When these 325 core genes were used to multiple sequence alignment following phylogenetic tree was drawn by neighbor-joining approach, it was found that marine strains occupy adjacent position on phylogram (Figure 4). The same observation also noticed when gene presence-absence based phylogenetic tree was drawn with same approach, based on how each of the genome contribute in the pan genome (Figure 5). Only strain that fall distant in position was *Brevibacterium* sp. BDJS002. Polyphyletic close phylogenetic relationship between marine strains

supported by both core and pan genome reveals that the marine strains were not diverged recently rather evolved through continuous adaptation in marine habitat.

Genomics of nutrient uptake, osmotic pressure regulation and resistance mechanisms to genotoxicity of sediment, enriched in marine strains

Number of core gene increased, when genome of marine strains was concerned, in comparison to the core genes for 138 genomes. When genome analysis was performed for 13 marine isolates of *Brevibacterium*, 1963 number of core genes represents the core genome. Highest percentages of core genes found to be distributed in, amino acid transport and metabolism COG category, signifying the importance of these genes in marine adaptation. Different strains of *Brevibacterium*, follow aerobic chemoorganoheterotrophic mode of nutrition (Bhadra et al. 2008; Lee 2008; Chen et al. 2016; Pei et al. 2021), uptake and utilization of readily available mono/oligomer of structural and functional cell component, from the environment is an adaptive strategy in energy limited environments (Stanley et al. 1987; Coffin et al. 1989).

Marine waterbody and its sediment system are the active areas, where organic compounds remineralization takes place, resulting bioavailable amino acids and short peptide chains, in water column and underneath sediment (Fernandes et al. 2014; Choi et al. 2022). Amino acid is available in aquatic environments in simple monomer, short peptide chains and proteins (Coffin et al. 1989). α - and β - amino acids along with their derivatives often used by bacteria as compatible solutes for osmoadaptation. Uptake of readily available amino acids from the surroundings and incorporating within the biomass is one of the adaptive features of marine adaptation to economically funneling available energy as microbes living in this habitat have to withstand the pressure of water column and high salinity (Stanley et al. 1987; Coffin et al. 1989). Along with the amino acid transport and metabolism, core genome of marine strains includes high percentages of core genes from carbohydrate transport and metabolism, and energy production and conversion COG category. Genes of both of these COG categories are help in proper energy budgeting of the microbial cell, by utilizing readily available compounds available in the surroundings. Polymeric carbohydrates and sugars also often used by microorganism as osmolyte to cope up with the higher osmotic pressure (Yancey 2020), thus transporter of them found to be adaptive strategy for marine habitat. Furthermore, for marine adaptation, enhancement of the core genes observed in the COG category concerning inorganic ion transport and metabolism. Exchange of inorganic ions with the surrounding environment is one of the important adaptations for marine habitat along with the transport of compatible solutes (Wood et al. 2001; Welsh 2020). Furthermore, for marine adaptation, addition of core genes observed in along the most of the COG categories (Figure 6B; Supplementary Table S6). Additional core genes found to be added in core genome for marine adaptation include mechanosensitive ion channel, proteins involved in proper folding of polypeptides in stressed condition, repairing machinery for DNA damage, membrane channel responsible for solute homeostasis of bacterial cytoplasm. In marine sediment different mixtures of chemical and organic compounds

causes damage to the dsDNA of the cell (Kammann et al. 2000), to overcome this genotoxic potential of sediment the damage repairing machinery found to be an important adaptive strategy for strains under *Brevibacterium*.

Marine province-specific genome evolution shed light on oceanic habitat evolution

Strains of *Brevibacterium*, living in seawater-sediment system of the three major marine provinces i.e. Atlantic Ocean, Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean found to bear three different sized core genomes consisting of core genes (Figure 7A). Core gene distribution in different COG categories for these three-province specific dataset not show a larger difference (Figure 7B) but in details they differ. Genomes from each of the marine province share additional number of core genes between themselves, along with the core genes those were observed for marine adaptation. Though interconnected through water body sediment system of individual oceanic region got isolated due its immensity. This indicate that marine adaptation is not an easy ubiquitous metabolic strategy for strains under the genus *Brevibacterium*, rather special genome-guided metabolisms need to be acquired. Isolated environment of each of the marine province affect the genome evolution for strains of *Brevibacterium*, revealing marine strains are not recently introduced microorganism rather evolved through divergence and evolution of marine habitat through different geological and plate tectonics.

For the adaptation in Indian Ocean province, core genome expansion includes genes having function in cell division regulation and determination of diameter of peptidoglycan layer. Different proteins involved in releasing supercoiling of DNA, non-homologous end joining DNA repair machinery, different transcriptional regulators and inorganic ion transporter protein are integrated in the core genome of the strains of Indian Ocean territory (Supplementary Table S10). The Indian Ocean harbor Arabian Sea OMZ and Bay of Bengal OMZ, the isolation site of strains of *Brevibacterium* were nearby regions of these OMZs. For adaptation of aerobic bacteria in stressed environment (O_2 limitation, nutrient availability, heavy metal enriched, variation of in situ temperature and higher salinity) cell size adjustment, DNA repair machinery, transcriptional regulation at different stages, is found to be important in different bacteria (Dai and Zhu 2018; Dupuy et al. 2019; Mathivanan et al. 2021; Pedraza-Reyes et al. 2024). The expanded core genome of two Arabian Sea isolates included genes concerning metabolism under carbon starvation, encoding arsenic resistant machinery, sodium ion and proton transporter and cold shock proteins (Supplementary Table S12). Adaptation in environments with changing nutrient availability, heavy metal abundance, wide temperature fluctuation and high osmotic pressure these metabolisms found to be important for survivability (Schultz and Matin 1991; Rosen et al. 1999; Zhang and Gross 2021). When genomes of any of the three marine provinces taken under consideration and largest closed circular genome of that dataset used as subject, on which other genomes of the same dataset mapped using BLAST algorithm (E-value cutoff was set to 0.0001), similar pattern in mapped-unmapped portion found, which further provides in between genomic relatedness (Figures 8, 9 and 10) of three marine provinces.

The two genomes of pure culture isolates *Brevibacterium* sp. BDJS002 and *Brevibacterium* sp. JSBI002 living in sediment of Arabian Sea OMZ, fall apart in both core genome- and pan genome-based phylogeny. Both of them

555 show maximum digital DNA-DNA hybridization value (dDDH) with different type strains (Table 1); but when
only genomes from Arabian Sea, were concerned these two strains share 2584 number of non-redundant core
genes (core genome size also increases from Indian_Ocean_Genomes dataset), indicating marine habitat play
pivotal role in shaping genome evolution through horizontal gene transfer to acquire niche specific metabolic
potential. With decreasing vastness of marine province, a greater number of genes included in the core genome
560 regardless of their species level taxonomic identity.

Searching for recently introduced genes within the genomes of marine isolates, through horizontal gene transfer
mechanism in genome specific unique gene set, reveals high genomic plasticity as genes from all the major
lineages i.e. Proteobacteria, Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes found to be included in the genome, encoding different
glycosyl transferases, endonucleases, and ion channels. Furthermore, the genes of viral origin also observed to be
565 incorporated in the genome of the marine isolates (Supplementary Table S13). The core and pan genome-based
analysis showed that by colonizing a geographical region, different strains of *Brevibacterium* share significant
number of core genes in their genome which bear marine geographical province-specific metabolic functions
(Figure 7A). It may also indicate that diversification of marine strains of *Brevibacterium* takes place along with
the evolution and spreading of marine habitat due to plate tectonics. As marine habitat especially oceanic sediment
570 system is a stable environment in respect of flowing waterbody or terrestrial habitat and imposes additional
environmental pressure for intruders, this may help to preserve evolutionary lineage of genomic traits. Genomics
with larger taxonomically diverse dataset have future research scope for study the pattern of marine habitat
evolution and underlying genome evolution.

575 SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supplementary information and data are available online in the form of a Word file named
Supplimentary_Information.docx, and an Excel file named Supplimentary_Dataset.xlsx.

580 DATA AVAILABILITY

GenBank accession numbers for the genomes under the study was presented in Supplementary Table 1.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

585 J.S. conceived the study, designed the bioinformatical experiments, interpreted the results, and wrote the paper.

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The study did not utilize any fund.

590 **COMPETING INTEREST**

The authors declare no competing interest.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Not applicable for this study

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FIGURE LEGENDS

710 **Figure 1.** Approximate geographical location from which sampling was reported to be done for isolation of 13 marine pure culture strains of *Brevibacterium*. White dots were assigned for strains those having proper geographical location from which isolation inoculum was obtained; while yellow dots were assigned for strains those having only reported major geographical provinces (i.e. Atlantic Ocean, Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean) from which isolation inoculum was obtained.

715 **Figure 2.** (A) Distribution of G+C percentages for all the 138 genomes of pure culture strains of *Brevibacterium*. (B) Genomic size distribution for all the 138 genomes of pure culture strains of *Brevibacterium*. In both of the plots red-filled shape denote genomic data derived from marine strains.

Figure 3. Core and pan genome plot of 138 genomes obtained from pure culture strains of *Brevibacterium*, representing one-by-one addition of the genome and changes in core and pan genome structure.

720 **Figure 4.** 325 core genes based phylogenetic tree for the 138 strains of *Brevibacterium*, created by neighbor-joining approach. Strains name written in red indicates pure culture isolates obtained from marine seawater/sediment and having proper geographical location of isolation site.

725 **Figure 5.** Pan genome based phylogenetic tree for the 138 strains of *Brevibacterium*, created by neighbor-joining approach. Gene presence and absence based binary pan-matrix was considered for depicting relation between all the 138 genomes. Similarity and dissimilarity in contribution of genes to pan genome (orthologous gene clusters) was used to calculate gene matrix. Strains name written in red indicates pure culture isolates obtained from marine seawater/sediment and having proper geographical location of isolation site.

Figure 6. (A) Distribution of core, accessory and unique genes of 138 genomes into different COG categories (B) Distribution of core, accessory and unique genes of 13 genomes of marine isolates, into different COG categories

730 **Figure 7.** (A) Schematic diagram of core genome size for all the 13 marine strains of *Brevibacterium* and variation between core genome size for strains living in different marine provinces. (B) Distribution of core genes of strains living in Atlantic, Indian and Pacific Ocean provinces, into different COG categories

735 **Figure 8.** Circular genome-genome mapping visualization for all the three genomes of Atlantic_Ocean_Genomes dataset. The inner to outer colored-ring represents, CDSs of *Brevibacterium atlanticum* WO024, mapped region of *Brevibacterium oceani* WW007 on *Brevibacterium atlanticum* WO024, mapped region of *Brevibacterium pigmentatum* YB235 on *Brevibacterium atlanticum* WO024. BLAST algorithm was used for mapping where E-value cutoff was set to 0.0001.

Figure 9. Circular genome-genome mapping visualization for all the six genomes of Indian_Ocean_Genomes dataset. The inner to outer colored-ring represents, CDSs of *Brevibacterium* sp. BDFS002, mapped region of

740 *Brevibacterium* sp. JSBI002 on *Brevibacterium* sp. BDJS002, mapped region of *Brevibacterium sediminis*
COD27 on *Brevibacterium* sp. BDJS002, mapped region of *Brevibacterium sediminis* FXJ8.269 on
Brevibacterium sp. BDJS002, mapped region of *Brevibacterium sediminis* CGMCC 1.15472 on *Brevibacterium*
sp. BDJS002, mapped region of *Brevibacterium oceani* BBH7 on *Brevibacterium* sp. BDJS002. BLAST
algorithm was used for mapping where E-value cutoff was set to 0.0001.

745 **Figure 10.** Circular genome-genome mapping visualization for all the four genomes of Pacific_Ocean_Genomes
dataset. The inner to outer colored-ring represents, CDSs of *Brevibacterium limosum* o2, mapped region of
Brevibacterium marinum DSM 18964 on *Brevibacterium limosum* o2, mapped region of *Brevibacterium* sp.
Marine on *Brevibacterium limosum* o2, mapped region of *Brevibacterium* sp. CCUG 69071 on *Brevibacterium*
limosum o2. BLAST algorithm was used for mapping where E-value cutoff was set to 0.0001.

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